

Anion Exchange Separation of Some Metal Ions in Aqueous-Acetone-Trichloroacetic Acid Media. Part—IV

S. V. KULKARNI*, S. S. JOSHI and S. K. SOMAN

Department of Chemistry, Shivaji University, Kolhapur-416 004

Manuscript received 29 September 1983, revised 30 May 1984, accepted 10 August 1984

Anion exchange chromatographic studies of Cd^{II}, Zn^{II}, Co^{II}, Cu^{II}, Ca^I, Mn^{II}, Mg^{II} and Ni^{II} on Dowex 21 K (Cl⁻ form) in mixed solvent systems were carried out. The efficiency of acetone-trichloroacetic acid (TCA) system is evaluated in terms of distribution coefficients and suggested the following selectivity sequence,

Methods have been developed for the separation of Ca/Mn/Mg/Ni from Cd/Zn/Co in binary mixtures. Many interesting sequential separations of metal ions from tertiary and quaternary mixtures are carried out. This ion exchange method is applied to the analysis of brass.

ION-exchange characteristics of metal ions have been studied in carboxylic acid media and several metal ions have successfully been separated on anion exchange resins. Anion exchange studies in buffered aqueous solutions of acetic, chloroacetic and dichloroacetic acid containing acetone were reported earlier¹⁻³. A systematic anion exchange chromatographic study of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II}, Mn^{II}, Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, Cu^{II} and Cd^{II} on Dowex 21 K in mixed water-acetone-trichloroacetic acid (TCA) solvent system is presented in this paper. The results include the separation of metal ions from binary, tertiary and quaternary mixtures and the technique is applied to the analysis of brass alloy.

Experimental

An anion exchange resin, Dowex 21 K in chloride form was used for all anion exchange distribution studies. The solutions of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II}, Mn^{II}, Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, Cu^{II} and Cd^{II} were prepared by dissolving their chlorides in distilled water and standardized complexometrically⁴.

Distribution studies were carried out using solutions (50 ml each) containing the metal ion and a mixture consisting of acetone, TCA and water. To this mixture 1 g resin was added and the batches were equilibrated by shaking for 24 h. The resin was filtered off and the filtrate was analysed for the metal ions. The distribution coefficients, K_D were calculated by using the equation

$$K_D = \frac{\text{meq. metal per g dry resin}}{\text{meq. metal per ml solution}}$$

For the chromatographic separations, the resin bed was prepared by making a slurry of the resin (≈ 15 g) in water and transferred to the graduated column. The synthetic mixture of metal ions was fed on the column. The metal ions were eluted by

suitable eluting agents (Tables 3-5). From the binary mixtures Mg/Cu/Mn/Ca/Ni-Co, Mg/Cu/Mn/Ca/Ni were eluted by 80% acetone-3 M TCA (eluent e) and Co was eluted by distilled water (eluent f). The mixtures Cu/Co/Mn/Ni/Mg/Ca-Cd were analysed and Cu/Co were eluted by 80% acetone +0.5 M TCA (eluent a), Mn/Ni/Mg/Ca by 60% acetone +0.5 M TCA (eluent d), and Cd by 50% acetone +0.1 M TCA (eluent c). Cu/Co/Mg/Ca were eluted by eluent a, Mn/Ni by eluent d, and Zn by 20% acetone +0.5 M TCA (eluent b) from the binary mixture Cu/Co/Mg/Ca/Mn/Ni-Zn. From tertiary mixtures Mg/Cu/Mn/Ca/Ni were eluted by eluent e, Co by 60% acetone +3 M TCA (eluent h), and Zn/Cd by eluent d and c, respectively. From quaternary mixtures Mg/Ca/Mn/Cu and Ni were eluted by eluent e, Co by eluent h, Zn by 0.1 M HCl (eluent g), and Cd by eluent c, and the effluents were estimated in 10 ml fractions.

Results and Discussion

The distribution coefficients of the metal ions under study were found out at 0.5, 1, 2, 3 M of TCA and 0, 20, 40, 60, 80 percentages of acetone. As most of the binary, tertiary, quaternary mixture separations are possible in 0.5 and 3 M TCA, the distribution coefficients only in these media are reported in Tables 1 and 2.

The effect of the concentration of TCA to the metal ion uptake by an anion exchanger is seen from the results presented in Tables 1 and 2. K_D values of Ni^{II}, Mn^{II}, Mg^{II} are low at 0.5 and 1 M TCA at all percentages of acetone, indicating the tendency of these ions to form less stable anionic complexes or not to form such complexes. This behaviour may lead to lesser or no exchange on an anion exchanger. The distribution coefficients of Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Co^{II} and Cu^{II} at 3 M TCA are greater than

TABLE 1—ANION EXCHANGE DISTRIBUTION COEFFICIENTS IN AQUEOUS ACETONE-TRICHLOROACETIC ACID (0.5 M) ON DOWEX 21 K (Cl⁻)

Ion	Acetone concentration % (v/v)				
	0	20	40	60	80
Co ^{II}	15	18	14	18	17
Ni ^{II}	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Zn ^{II}	18	25	31	59	738
Mn ^{II}	3	1	3	NA	NA
Mg ^{II}	NA	3	NA	2	NA
Ca ^{II}	28	29	29	32	28
Cu ^{II}	19	25	32	19	25
Cd ^{II}	NA	NA	3	97	513

TABLE 2—ANION EXCHANGE DISTRIBUTION COEFFICIENTS IN AQUEOUS ACETONE-TRICHLOROACETIC ACID (3 M) ON DOWEX 21 K (Cl⁻)

Ion	Acetone concentration % (v/v)				
	0	20	40	60	80
Co ^{II}	82	91	108	134.6	2460
Ni ^{II}	NA	3	3	3	5
Zn ^{II}	52	86	102	206	5468
Mn ^{II}	2	2	2	4	4
Mg ^{II}	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Ca ^{II}	12	16	16	24	27
Cu ^{II}	62	62	82	103	140
Cd ^{II}	32	102	186	690	5104

those at 0.5 M TCA at respective acetone percentages. Cu^{II} shows considerable rise (≈ 3 to 4 times) in K_D at 3 M TCA indicating increasing tendency of complex formation at higher concentration of the acid.

The distribution coefficients of Zn^{II}, Co^{II}, Cd^{II} increase with the rise in acetone concentration. The profound or better effect is observed in 40-80% acetone range and at 3 M TCA. This behaviour is according to the fact that the presence of a less polar solvent mixed with water enhances the extent of complex formation^{5,6}.

There is no measurable change in K_D values of Co^{II} in 0.5 M TCA, upto 60% acetone-1 M TCA. In 2 M TCA upto 40% acetone the value of K_D is ≈ 50 , showing that the partition of metal ion in solvent and resin phase is nearly equal. The distribution coefficient increases continuously in 3 M TCA and reaches maximum ($K_D = 2460$) at 80% acetone. The same type of blue coloured anionic complex of Co^{II} was also obtained in 80% acetone-3 M acetic acid¹/chloroacetic acid²/dichloroacetic acid³. Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} show maximum K_D under the same conditions. The K_D data of the metal ions in Tables 1 and 2 suggest the following selectivity sequence,

Cd $\gg$ Zn $>$ Ca $>$ Cu $>$ Co $>$ Mn $\approx$ Mg $\approx$ Ni (0.5 M TCA)
 Cd $\gg$ Zn $>$ Co $>$ Cu $>$ Ca $>$ Mn $\approx$ Mg $\approx$ Ni (3 M TCA)

As compared to K_D data reported earlier¹⁻³ it is observed that Cu^{II} gives higher values in 3 M TCA than acetic, chloroacetic, dichloroacetic acids. The distribution tendencies of Cu^{II} on an anion exchanger is thus modified by TCA in presence of water miscible organic solvent (acetone).

The results of quantitative separation of synthetic binary, tertiary and quaternary mixtures are presented in Tables 3, 4 and 5, respectively. Mg, Cu, Mn, Ca and Ni are eluted first as these ions are weakly bound to the resin in comparison to Co, Cd

TABLE 3—QUANTITATIVE SEPARATION OF SYNTHETIC BINARY MIXTURES

FIRST ION IN THE MIXTURE IS ELUTED WHILE SECOND ION IS RETAINED

Sl. no.	Mixture	Metal ion eluted	Eluting agent*	m mol taken	m mol found
1.	Mg ^{II} + Co ^{II}	Mg ^{II}	e	0.175	0.175
		Co ^{II}	f	0.244	0.244
2.	Cu ^{II} + Co ^{II}	Cu ^{II}	e	0.240	0.210
		Co ^{II}	f	0.244	0.244
3.	Mn ^{II} + Co ^{II}	Mn ^{II}	e	0.211	0.210
		Co ^{II}	f	0.244	0.244
4.	Ca ^{II} + Co ^{II}	Ca ^{II}	e	0.184	0.192
		Co ^{II}	f	0.162	0.161
5.	Ni ^{II} + Co ^{II}	Ni ^{II}	e	0.220	0.229
		Co ^{II}	f	0.244	0.244
6.	Cu ^{II} + Cd ^{II}	Cu ^{II}	a	0.256	0.252
		Cd ^{II}	c	0.251	0.251
7.	Mn ^{II} + Cd ^{II}	Mn ^{II}	d	0.230	0.226
		Cd ^{II}	c	0.239	0.241
8.	Co ^{II} + Cd ^{II}	Co ^{II}	a	0.50	0.249
		Cd ^{II}	c	0.239	0.241
9.	Ni ^{II} + Cd ^{II}	Ni ^{II}	d	0.262	0.260
		Cd ^{II}	c	0.239	0.241
10.	Mg ^{II} + Cd ^{II}	Mg ^{II}	d	0.250	0.241
		Cd ^{II}	c	0.239	0.041
11.	Ca ^{II} + Cd ^{II}	Ca ^{II}	d	0.241	0.240
		Cd ^{II}	c	0.239	0.241
12.	Cu ^{II} + Zn ^{II}	Cu ^{II}	a	0.256	0.252
		Zn ^{II}	b	0.201	0.202
13.	Co ^{II} + Zn ^{II}	Co ^{II}	a	0.234	0.246
		Zn ^{II}	b	0.200	0.166
14.	Mn ^{II} + Zn ^{II}	Mn ^{II}	d	0.230	0.228
		Zn ^{II}	b	0.201	0.202
15.	Ni ^{II} + Zn ^{II}	Ni ^{II}	d	0.262	0.261
		Zn ^{II}	b	0.201	0.202
16.	Mg ^{II} + Zn ^{II}	Mg ^{II}	a	0.248	0.252
		Zn ^{II}	b	0.201	0.202
17.	Ca ^{II} + Zn ^{II}	Ca ^{II}	a	0.254	0.268
		Zn ^{II}	b	0.201	0.202

* Abbreviation as in Table 5.

TABLE 4—QUANTITATIVE SEPARATION OF SYNTHETIC TERNARY MIXTURES

Sl. no.	Mixture	Metal ion eluted	Eluting agent*	m mol taken	m mol found
1.	Mg ^{II} + Co ^{II} + Zn ^{II}	Mg ^{II}	e	0.204	0.154
		Co ^{II}	h	0.162	0.161
		Zn ^{II}	d	0.243	0.203
2.	Cu ^{II} + Co ^{II} + Zn ^{II}	Cu ^{II}	e	0.210	0.211
		Co ^{II}	h	0.162	0.161
		Zn ^{II}	d	0.243	0.203
3.	Mn ^{II} + Co ^{II} + Zn ^{II}	Mn ^{II}	e	0.210	0.200
		Co ^{II}	h	0.162	0.161
		Zn ^{II}	d	0.243	0.203
4.	Ca ^{II} + Co ^{II} + Zn ^{II}	Ca ^{II}	e	0.196	0.145
		Co ^{II}	h	0.162	0.161
		Zn ^{II}	d	0.243	0.203
5.	Ni ^{II} + Co ^{II} + Zn ^{II}	Ni ^{II}	e	0.245	0.259
		Co ^{II}	h	0.162	0.161
		Zn ^{II}	d	0.243	0.203
6.	Mg ^{II} + Co ^{II} + Cd ^{II}	Mg ^{II}	e	0.204	0.158
		Co ^{II}	h	0.162	0.161
		Cd ^{II}	c	0.242	0.223
7.	Cu ^{II} + Co ^{II} + Cd ^{II}	Cu ^{II}	e	0.210	0.221
		Co ^{II}	h	0.162	0.161
		Cd ^{II}	c	0.242	0.223
8.	Mn ^{II} + Co ^{II} + Cd ^{II}	Mn ^{II}	e	0.210	0.221
		Co ^{II}	h	0.162	0.161
		Cd ^{II}	c	0.242	0.223
9.	Ca ^{II} + Co ^{II} + Cd ^{II}	Ca ^{II}	e	0.196	0.148
		Co ^{II}	h	0.162	0.161
		Cd ^{II}	c	0.242	0.223
10.	Ni ^{II} + Co ^{II} + Cd ^{II}	Ni ^{II}	e	0.245	0.255
		Co ^{II}	h	0.162	0.161
		Cd ^{II}	c	0.242	0.223

* Abbreviation as in Table 5.

and Zn. The eluting agents for Mg, Cu, Mn, Ca and Ni depend on the other co-ion in binary mixtures (Table 3). The clear cut separation of Co/Ni/Mn/Mg/Ca/Cu-Cd is shown in Fig. 1. Co^{II} is eluted by distilled water, showing that decomplexation takes place quickly by the cheapest solvent like water. The element in tertiary mixtures are separated by selective sorption method. The first metal ion Mg/Cu/Mn/Ca/Ni is eluted by e, the second metal ion Co by h, and the third ion Zn/Cd is eluted by c and d, respectively. The separation of four metal ions is attempted and the successful results are obtained. In these ion-exchange separations the first metal is different, *i.e.* Mg or Ca or Mn or Cu or Ni, the other metal ions Co, Zn and Cd are common and are eluted by h, g, c, respectively. The separation of Mn/Cu/Ni is better than Mg/Ca from these tertiary mixtures.

TABLE 5—QUANTITATIVE SEPARATION OF SYNTHETIC QUATERNARY MIXTURES IN TCA

Sl. no.	Mixture	Metal ion eluted	Eluting agent*	m mol taken	m mol found
1.	Mg ^{II} + Co ^{II} + Zn ^{II} + Cd ^{II}	Mg ^{II}	e	0.204	0.154
		Co ^{II}	h	0.162	0.161
		Zn ^{II}	g	0.203	0.164
		Cd ^{II}	c	0.242	0.223
		Ca ^{II}	e	0.196	0.145
2.	Ca ^{II} + Co ^{II} + Zn ^{II} + Cd ^{II}	Ca ^{II}	e	0.196	0.145
		Co ^{II}	h	0.162	0.161
		Zn ^{II}	g	0.203	0.164
		Cd ^{II}	c	0.242	0.223
		Mn ^{II}	e	0.210	0.200
3.	Mn ^{II} + Co ^{II} + Zn ^{II} + Cd ^{II}	Mn ^{II}	e	0.210	0.200
		Co ^{II}	h	0.162	0.161
		Zn ^{II}	g	0.203	0.164
		Cd ^{II}	c	0.242	0.223
		Cu ^{II}	e	0.210	0.211
4.	Cu ^{II} + Co ^{II} + Zn ^{II} + Cd ^{II}	Cu ^{II}	e	0.210	0.211
		Co ^{II}	h	0.162	0.161
		Zn ^{II}	g	0.203	0.164
		Cd ^{II}	c	0.242	0.223
		Ni ^{II}	e	0.245	0.230
5.	Ni ^{II} + Co ^{II} + Zn ^{II} + Cd ^{II}	Ni ^{II}	e	0.245	0.230
		Co ^{II}	h	0.162	0.161
		Zn ^{II}	g	0.203	0.164
		Cd ^{II}	c	0.242	0.223
		Ca ^{II}	e	0.196	0.148

* a - 80% Acetone - 0.5 M TCA ; b - 20% acetone - 0.5 M TCA ; c - 50% acetone - 0.1 M TCA ; d - 60% acetone - 0.5 M TCA ; e - 80% acetone - 3 M TCA ; f - distilled water ; g - 0.1 M HCl ; h - 60% acetone - 3 M TCA.

Analysis of standard brass sample : About 0.3 g brass alloy was weighed out accurately and dissolved by heating with HNO₃ and H₂SO₄ (1 : 1). Care was taken to remove all H₂SO₄ and the solution was finally fumed until only about 1 ml HNO₃ remained. After dilution, any remaining insoluble residue was separated by filtration, and the filtrate was kept for the column separation. The solution was passed through the column. The ion-exchange separation and the determinations of Cu and Zn were then carried out as described for the analysis of synthetic mixture. The separation of Cu and Zn from brass alloy was also carried out by standard procedure and Cu was estimated volumetrically⁷ and zinc gravimetrically⁷. The results obtained by both the methods are presented in Table 6.

 TABLE 6—ESTIMATION OF Cu^{II} AND Zn^{II} IN BRASS ALLOY

Method	Weight of alloy taken g	Amount of Cu g	% Cu	Amount of Zn g	% Zn
Standard method	0.353	0.217	61.3	0.133	37.6
Ion-exchange method	0.353	0.216	61.2	0.137	38.9

Fig. 1. Elution curves of Cu (—○—)/Co (—□—)/Ni (—●—)/Mn (—●—)/Mg (—■—)/Ca (—△—)/Cd (—○—).

The described method provides an excellent means for the quantitative separation of Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} from each other and for the accurate determination of these elements in brass alloy. The attractive feature of the separation procedure is that only a single anion exchange column is employed and no further purification steps are necessary.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (S.S.J.) is thankful to the C.S.I.R., New Delhi for the award of Senior Research Fellowship.

References

1. S. V. KULKARNI, S. K. SOMAN and S. S. JOSHI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, 60, 779.
2. S. V. KULKARNI, S. K. SOMAN and S. S. JOSHI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, communicated.
3. S. V. KULKARNI, S. K. SOMAN and S. S. JOSHI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1984, 61, 634.
4. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longmans, London, 1961, p. 194.
5. R. W. GABALE and N. P. STROBEL, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1965, 69, 513.
6. R. P. BHATNAGAR and N. C. JAIN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, 57, 168.
7. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longmans, London, 1961, p. 629.